

Contributions to knowledge on the distribution of *Leucospis dorsigera* Fabricius, 1775 (Chalcidoidea: Leucospidae) in Poland and Belarus

Materiały do poznania rozmieszczenia *Leucospis dorsigera* FABRICIUS, 1775 (Chalcidoidea: Leucospidae) w Polsce i Białorusi

Artsiom M. OSTROVSKY

Department of Public Health and Health Care with the course of the Faculty of Professional Development and Retraining, Gomel State Medical University,

5 Lange St., 246000, Gomel, Belarus, e-mail: arti301989@mail.ru

SUMMARY. Two new localities of *Leucospis dorsigera* FABRICIUS, 1775, a rare wasp species in the fauna of Poland and Belarus, are presented. Specimens of the species were collected in June 2019 in Klimonty (Poland: Mazovian Lowland) and July – August 2024 in Gomel (SE Belarus). Brief information about its known distribution in both countries is given.

KEY WORDS: Hymenoptera, rape wasp species, new localities, faunistics, Eastern Europe.

Leucospis dorsigera FABRICIUS, 1775 is the only known representative of the family Leucospidae in Poland and Belarus, so far. This is a rare species than endangered in relation to the disappearance of its habitats: old, dying, and sunlit trees and wooden buildings. The larvae of *L. dorsigera* are parasitoids of bee larvae of the family Megachilidae (WIŚNIEWSKI 2004), occasionally also as a hyperparasitoid of the barbel beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) through Darwin wasps from the subfamily Xoridinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) (HESAMI et al. 2005). The species figures on the Polish Red Data Book of Animals in the category VU (vulnerable species) (WIŚNIEWSKI 2004).

In this note, two new localities of *L. dorsigera* in Poland and Belarus are presented:

- Poland, FC08 Klimonty, on the outer wall of the wooden shed, 24 VI 2019, 1♀ (Fig. A);
- Belarus, UD61 Gomel, on flowers of *Solidago canadensis* L., 23 VII 2024, 1♀ (Fig. B), 2 VIII 2024, 1♀ (Fig. C).

The material was collected and identified by the author and is housed in his personal collection.

In Poland, *L. dorsigera* was found for the first time at the end of the 18th century in Silesia (PANZER 1798). However, BOUČEK (1959, 1974) did not include this species in the Polish fauna. The occurrence of the species was confirmed by SZCZEPAŃSKI (1964) based

on two female specimens caught in 1947 in the village Niezgodna, Milicz district in the valley of the Barycz river. Subsequently, in the article of WIŚNIEWSKI & ŻYŁA (1996) three more localities of *L. dorsigera* in southern Poland were presented. The last statement of this species in Poland was included in the article by MARCZAK et al. (2012), where seven new localities in central and eastern Poland were presented. A specimen of *L. dorsigera* captured in Klimonty (Mazowsze) confirms the limit of the north-eastern distribution of the species in Poland.

In Belarus, *L. dorsigera* has so far been known from two findings from the Bragin district of the Gomel region (OSTROVSKY 2020). The record of *L. dorsigera* from Gomel city enlarges the range of this species in Belarus by 120 km north. This is probably connected with the rapid warming of the climate in recent years and the distinct aridization of the south-east of Belarus (OSTROVSKY 2017). Thus, for *L. dorsigera* the north-east limit of distribution in Europe moved more north.

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Fig. *Leucospis dorsigera*, females:
 A – 24 June 2019, Klimonty, Mazowsze, Poland;
 B – 23 July 2024, Gomel, Belarus;
 C – 2 August 2024, Gomel, Belarus

Ryc. Samice *Leucospis dorsigera*:
 A – 24 VI 2019 Klimonty, Mazowsze;
 B – 23 VII 2024 Homel, Białoruś;
 C – 2 VIII 2024 Homel, Białoruś

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